

**Identification of reciprocal adhesion genes in pathogenic and non-pathogenic
*Pseudomonas***

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SUMMARY

We have used a combination of *in silico* and large-scale mutagenesis approaches to expand our current knowledge of the genetic determinants used by *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440 to attach to surfaces. We first identified *in silico* orthologs that have been annotated in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as potentially involved in attachment. In this search 67 paired-related genes of *P. putida* KT2440 and *P. aeruginosa* were identified as associated to adhesion. To test the potential role of the corresponding gene products in adhesion, 37 knock-out mutants of KT2440, available in the *Pseudomonas* Reference Culture Collection, were analyzed with regard to their ability to form biofilms in polystyrene microtiter plates; of these, 7 mutants were deficient in adhesion. Since mutants in all potential adhesion genes were not available, we generated a genome-wide collection of mutants made of 7680 independent mini-Tn5 insertions and tested them for the formation of biofilm on polystyrene microtiter plates. Eighteen clones that exhibited a reduction of at least 3-fold in biofilm biomass formation were considered candidate mutants in adhesion determinants. DNA sequencing of the insertion site identified 5 other new genes involved in adhesion. Phenotypic characterization of the 12 mutants showed that the inactivated proteins were required for attachment to biotic and abiotic surfaces. This combined approach has allowed us to identify new proteins with a role in *P. putida* adhesion, including the global regulator RpoN and GacS, the lectin-like protein LecA, PstS, and a protein of unknown function (PP1633). The remaining mutants corresponded to functions known or predicted to participate in adhesion based on previous evidences, such as the large adhesion LapA, LapF, and flagellar proteins. *In silico* analysis showed this set of genes is well conserved in all sequenced *P. putida* strains, and that at least 8 reciprocal genes involved in attachment are shared by *P. putida* and *P. aeruginosa*.

INTRODUCTION

Pseudomonads are ubiquitous gram-negative bacteria characterized by a highly versatile metabolism, aerobic respiration, and motility. The key to the ubiquitous distribution of these bacteria is their genomic plasticity and the use of highly sophisticated regulatory mechanisms to adapt to changes in the local environment (Mathee *et al.*, 2008; Winsor *et al.*, 2009; Rodríguez-Palenzuela *et al.*, 2010; Wu *et al.*, 2010).

Bacteria of the species *Pseudomonas putida* are of interest for environmental, industrial and agricultural uses (Ramos *et al.*, 1994; Ramos *et al.*, 2009; 2011; REF). *Pseudomonas putida* colonizes plant root surfaces and the surrounding soil region (rhizosphere) in a mutualistic association, in which the bacteria thrive thanks to nutrients exudated by plant roots, and plant growth is favored by *P. putida* bacteria due to the solubilization of phosphate and iron, production of plant hormone precursors, inhibition of growth of fungal pathogens and induction of systemic resistance (Meyer *et al.*, 2011-AEM; Matilla *et al.*, 2007; Matilla *et al.*, 2006?; Matilla *et al.*, 2011a; Matilla *et al.*, 2011b; Segura *et al.*, 2009a; Segura *et al.*, 2009b). The strain *P. putida* KT2440, a derivative of the soil isolate mt-2, colonizes the rhizosphere of agronomically relevant plants at high population densities and is considered a model system to understand plant–microbe interactions (Molina *et al.*, 2000).

The adhesion of bacteria to seeds is considered a key factor in agricultural uses of microorganisms, since this facilitates the subsequent proliferation of bacteria attached to the surface and favors colonization of the root system once the plant starts to develop. Consequently root colonization and survival of *P. putida* in the rhizosphere of plants, along with bacterial responses to root exudates, are being studied at the molecular level (Rainey, 1999; Kandasamy *et al.*, Proteome Science; Petersen *et al.*, 2009; Martínez-Gil *et al.*, 2010; Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008; Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2011).

Mutants defective in attachment to biotic and abiotic surfaces have been isolated and characterized in different *Pseudomonas* species (Harsem *et al.*, 2010; López *et al.*, 2010; Mikkelsen *et al.*, 2011; Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008). Early studies by DeFlaun and coworkers revealed that some *P. fluorescens* mutants deficient in flagellum biosynthesis did not attach to soil particles and were defective in attachment to seeds (DeFlaun *et al.*, 1990; DeFlaun *et al.*, 1994). Further to this study, Espinosa-Urgel *et al.* (2000) designed a strategy to identify proteins specifically involved in adhesion of *P. putida* cells to plant seeds, and reported the phenotypic and molecular characterization of mutants of this strain deficient in adhesion to corn seeds. Some of these mutants and their ulterior analysis (Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008) identified a number of surface and membrane proteins that include two large calcium-binding protein named LapA and LapF, and the outer membrane protein of a potential type II secretion system. Here, we report a combined *in silico* and mutagenesis approach that has allowed us to identify 12 proteins involved in adhesion of *P. putida* to abiotic and biotic surfaces. While some of these proteins have been previously described in *Pseudomonas* as adhesion determinants and therefore were not unexpected, a new set of proteins were identified as playing a role in attachment to solid surfaces in *P. putida*.

RESULTS

***In silico* genome-scale homology search and analysis of available knock-out mutants regarding their ability to form biofilms.** *Pseudomonas putida* and *P. aeruginosa* are phylogenetically closely related microorganisms whose metabolic networks have been reconstructed *in silico* through genome-wide comparison and identification of the genes that encode enzymes that carry out the same reaction. This set of orthologous genes is called “reciprocal genes” (Oberhardt *et al.*, 2011).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a pathogenic microbe and some matters related to adhesion and biofilm formation have been analyzed in detail (Sauer and Kamper, 2001; Rändler *et al.*, 2010; Kirkeby *et al.*, 2007; Girand *et al.*, 2009; Chemani *et al.*, 2009). In contrast, few studies have analyzed surface adhesion in the saprophytic *P. putida* KT2440 strain (Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008; Espinosa-Urgel *et al.*, 2001; Martínez-Gil *et al.*, 2010). We reasoned that the "reciprocal gene" approach used to define metabolic networks could be extended to proteins other than enzymes, and centered our attention in the identification of new *P. putida* adhesion genes based on knowledge derived from *P. aeruginosa*. Using BLAST, we searched the *P. putida* KT2440 genome for adhesion genes using as a query all sequences of *P. aeruginosa* annotated in www.pseudomonas.org as potentially involved in adhesion/biofilm formation/motility/attachment. The metric for comparing BLAST matches was the score of the highest-scoring pair (Altschul *et al.*, 1990, Oberhardt *et al.*, 2011); a *P. putida* gene was considered reciprocal in the BLAST search performed with one of the *P. aeruginosa* genes as the query sequence when the *P. putida* gene was reported as the first hit, and when the proteins exhibited >40% identity at the protein level. Subsequently the *P. putida* genes thus identified were used as the query sequence to confirm that the reciprocal gene was present in *P. aeruginosa*. With this approach, a single gene can have at most one reciprocal gene. A total of 67 such pairs of reciprocal genes were identified (see Table 1).

To ascertain the role of these genes in adhesion, we made use of a mini-Tn5 collection of mutants of *P. putida* KT2440 available at the *Pseudomonas* Reference Culture Collection, in which the gene interrupted by the mini-Tn5 has been identified by sequencing the DNA adjacent to the insertion site (Duque *et al.*, 2007). In this collection, mutants in almost 50% of all ORFs are currently available, and in fact we

found 37 knock-out mutants in potential adhesion “reciprocal genes”. This set of knock-out mutants and the parental strain were tested for adhesion to polystyrene microtiter plates essentially as described by O’Toole and Kolter (O’Toole and Kolter, 1998(a,b), see also Experimental Procedures). Biofilm formation was analyzed after 6 h of growth on LB medium or M9 medium with glucose as a carbon source. Attached cells were stained with crystal violet and quantified (after solubilization of the crystal violet stain) by measuring absorbance at 540 nm. The results showed that 7 mutants had defects in biofilm formation, regardless of the growth medium. The identified mutants corresponded to the global regulatory proteins GacS and RpoN, four genes related to flagellum biosynthesis (*fliF*, *fliD*, *fliC*, *flhB*), and the ORF encoding PP1661, which has a domain with high similarity to the *lecA* gene of *P. aeruginosa* (Diggle *et al.*, 2006; Bazire *et al.*, 2010; Chemani *et al.*, 2009).

Construction of a genome-wide collection of *P. putida* and screening for clones defective in adhesion. Because the number of mutants with knocked-out genes related to attachment available in the PRCC was lower than the number of potential “reciprocal genes”, because *P. putida* could use adhesion factors others than those used by *P. aeruginosa* and because these microbes often inhabit different niches, we decided to generate a bank of random mutants of KT2440 and search for specific functions involved in the initial steps of attachment. To this end KT2440 was mutagenized by random insertion of mini-Tn5-Km (de Lorenzo *et al.*, 1990), and a pool of >10 000 kanamycin-resistant mutants were selected in minimal medium to avoid the isolation of auxotrophs. Twelve colonies were randomly chosen and Southern blot used to test for the independent character of the mini-Tn5 insertion. Upon confirming the independent insertion of the mini-Tn5 in each mutant and the absence of siblings, 15360 colonies

were spotted on solid agar plates. These clones were then tested individually for their ability to attach to polystyrene in 96-well microtiter plates. All clones that produced 2- to 3-fold less biofilm biomass than the parental strain were retained and retested on 24-well plates to facilitate the identification of mutants. After these two rounds 18 potential mutants were identified. Subsequently, the DNA sequence adjacent to the insertion site of the mini-Tn5 was determined and the nature of the gene interrupted in the knock-out mutant established. Several of the mutants corresponded to genes identified previously as encoding functions relevant for attach to maize seeds and abiotic surfaces (LapA, LapF, LapH [PP0805]) a protein presumably involved in secretion of LapF; other mutants corresponded to orthologous genes and for which mutants were available in the PRCC bank (FliC, FliD, FliF, FlhB). We also found a mutant in the *pstS* gene which had been identified *in silico* as a “reciprocal gene”, but no mutant was available in PRCC. This indicated that the collection of mutants and the screening test had good resolution. In addition to these genes, one different mutant with an insertion in a previously non-inactivated gene was also found that corresponded to PP1633, making a total of 12 loci as potentially able to encode proteins that affect *P. putida* attachment to polystyrene (Table 2).

Although all 12 mutants were able to grow on minimal medium with glucose and no auxotrophy could be linked to the decrease in attachment, to rule out that defects in adhesion were related to defects in metabolism, the parental strain and mutants were phenotypically characterized using a phenomics platform developed previously in our laboratory (Daniels *et al.*, 2010 See also Supplementary Material). All mutants but one exhibited the same pattern of C, N and S utilization as the parental strain. Metabolic differences were associated to deficiency in the *rpoN* gene. The RpoN mutant, in agreement with previous studies (Köhler *et al.*, 1989; Hervás *et al.*, 2010; Hervás *et al.*,

2009) exhibited a reduced ability to use a number of C and N sources including dipeptides abundant in root exudates. Since the RpoN mutant grew on LB medium and on minimal M9 medium with glucose at rates similar to those of the wild type, it was retained for further study.

The 12 genes required for adhesion in *P. putida* were grouped in five categories based on the general function of the protein (Table 2), namely, 1) mutants deficient in large adhesion proteins (LapF/LapA/PP0805), 2) mutants deficient in flagellum structural proteins, 3) mutants altered in proteins that control gene expression (GacS, and RpoN), 4) PP1661, which has a lectin A domain, and 5) two proteins of unknown function, one of them annotated as a phosphate transporter (PstS or PP5329) and the other one annotated as a hypothetical protein (PP1633) with functional domains related to oxidoreductases. In general, we found that LapA, LapF and LecA were less efficient in attaching to polystyrene plates and that the amount of biofilm formed was at least 10-fold lower than that produced by the parental strain, while the rest of mutants were only 2- to 3-fold less efficient in attachment than the parental strain.

Attachment of *P. putida* isogenic mutants to abiotic and biotic surfaces. We also tested biofilm formation of KT2440 and all the mutants identified above on different abiotic surfaces. These experiments were performed essentially as described above for polystyrene microtiter dishes, but in this series we also used polypropylene (Sterilin tubes), borosilicate glass (Pyrex tubes) and common glass surfaces. Biofilm formation was also analyzed after 6 h of growth in LB by staining with crystal violet. The results revealed that all 12 mutants showed defects in biofilm formation on all four surfaces (Figure 1 shows the results for one mutant in each of the 5 groups of functions). This

indicates that general functions required for attachment were affected in all the clones regardless of the abiotic surface tested.

To test whether the mutations that affect adhesion to abiotic surfaces affected adhesion to biotic surfaces, attachment to corn seeds and leaves of *Vinca major* plants was assayed. To this end the 12 mutants and the parental strain were grown on LB medium and the assays were done as described in Materials and Methods. The seed and leaf adhesion results indicated that all selected mutants, except the GacS PP1650 mutants were less efficient in adhering to corn seeds and leaves of *Vinca* than the parental strain (Table 3). It should be noted that of all mutants, the LapA one was significantly less efficient attaching to seeds than the others, while the trend was opposite regarding attachment to leaves. Therefore, some our results are of relevance and points that the mutants identified as deficient in adherence to abiotic surface were also less efficient in attachment to alive surfaces too (Table 3).

Transcriptomic analysis reveals that most adhesion genes are expressed glucose constitutively. Since a large number of adhesion genes are required, but their contribution to adhesion is different a hypothesis is that they could be expressed at different levels in cells. To analyse gene expression we analyzed global transcriptomic profiles of *P. putida* cells growing on LB medium or M9 minimal medium with glucose. To this end total RNA was extracted, cDNA was synthesized and labelled with the fluorosphore Cy3 and hybridized against a microarray that contains a 50-mer oligonucleotide that covers all ORFs of KT2440. Expression was recorded as the intensity of fluorescence of each gene and subsequently, we compared the expression level of each of the adhesion genes that we identified *in vivo* with two internal calibrators, the *gltA* gene (citrate synthase; relative level 9880-17700 units), whose

expression is essential under all growth conditions for this strict aerobe, and *pobA* (*p*-hydroxybenzoate hydroxylase; relative level 640-920 units), which is a gene known to be induced in response to *p*-hydroxybenzoate and which is not expressed in cells growing in LB on M9 with glucose. We found that the expression level, given as fluorescence intensities, of most of the experimentally identified adhesion genes were higher than that of *pobA* (Suppl. Fig. 1). This confirms that the genes identified as involved in adhesion under a specific are indeed transcribed under the culture conditions used for selection. It should be noted that the *pstS* gene was expressed in LB medium that has no add inorganic phosphate, while its expression was switch off in phosphate-rich M9 medium. This suggests that PstS role can be relevant under phosphate-starvation conditions. The LapF gene was in general expressed at a low level, and this can be related to their proposed role of cell-to-cell contact in the biofilm rather than a direct role in attachment. Importantly, the information regarding gene expression level should not be misinterpreted in regard to the actual proteins levels. In fact, it has been well established that, in yeast growing on glucose, the absolute mRNA levels of genes involved in the biosynthesis of amino acids do not reflect actual fluxes since other processes, such as post-transcriptional regulatory strategies, protein stability, are utilized to fine-tune protein levels in order to allow for balanced growth of the cells (Moxley *et al.*, 2009). A similar observation has been recently made in relation to the level of expression of the *psl* and *pel* clusters and the amount of exopolysaccharides produced by *P. aeruginosa* (Parsek – EMI – In press), what confirms that transcription levels cannot be directly translated into protein or product levels.

Analysis of biofilm formation by microscopy. Defects in attachment to surfaces were expected to lead to lower surface coverage in biofilm assays on glass cover slips. To test

this hypothesis the parental strain cells and mutant cells (5×10^7 CFU/ml) were spotted on a glass cover slip and incubated at room temperature for 6 h, and then surface coverage was analyzed by light microscopic observation and photographic recording of biofilm formation. In agreement with previous observations (Espinosa-Urgel *et al.*, 2000; Hinsa *et al.*, 2003; Martinez-Gil *et al.*, 2010), we found that LapA (See Figure 2) and LapF mutants (not shown) were deficient in biofilm formation; limited biofilm formation was also seen with other mutants such as GacS, PP1661, FhlB, PP1633 (Figure 2). Since biofilm formation involves more than attachment and also requires proliferation, we suggest that the set of genes we identified here are related to surface attachment and colonization.

To determine whether the attachment functions are of relevance in colonization of the rhizosphere, a number of mutants of each of the five adhesion groups were selected for colonization assays in competition or not with the parental strain. The strains chosen were LapA and LapF mutants from group 1, a mutant deficient in flagellum biosynthesis (FliC), the two mutants in the global regulators and GacS, the PP1661 mutant and the PP1663 mutant. The results showed that the mutant strains in sterile soil established in plant roots at cell densities similar to those of the parental strain. These results suggest that the 12 interrupted genes, although specifically involved in attachment to biotic and abiotic surfaces, are not essential for proliferation in the bacteria's natural niche, where *P. putida* grows at the expense of root exudates (data not shown). However, when the strains were competed with the parental strain the level of establishment in the rhizosphere was always lower than that of the parental strain. This indicates that attachment is a relevant requisite for establish out in the plant roots.

Electron Microscopy. Pending

DISCUSSION

Bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* are characterized by their ability to colonize a wide variety of niches; strains of the species *P. fluorescens* and *P. putida* are typically saprophytic soil inhabitants, while *P. syringae* and *P. aeruginosa* are recognized as plant and animal pathogens, respectively. The genomes of a number of strains of different species of this genus have been sequenced, being their size in the range of 5.7 Mb to 6.2 Mb. Vodovar *et al.* (2006) and Lalucat *et al.* (2007 *Pseudomonas* vol 6) indicated that around half of the proteins encoded by the genome of different *Pseudomonas* species are shared by all *Pseudomonas* strains sequenced so far, and that this set of common proteins, and therefore their coding genes probably constitute the core genome of the genus *Pseudomonas*. Oberhardt *et al.* (2011) carried out a global-scale comparison of the metabolic networks of *P. putida* and *P. aeruginosa* to better define common catabolic and anabolic pathways in these two microbes. Their approach was based on the identification of the so-called reciprocal genes (proteins), i.e. orthologous genes (enzymes) that encode (carry out) the same reaction. In this study we have extended this approach to identify potential reciprocal genes involved in adhesion, and also screened a genome-wide mini-Tn5 mutant collection for functional identification of genes that encode proteins relevant for attachment. The combination of *in silico* analysis, literature review and characterization of the mutants isolated in this study allowed us to identify 12 genes that encode functions related to attachment. Since in the mutant library we analyzed, a single random insertion is estimated to have occurred once in every 400 nucleotides, the probability to hit any gene is >99% and therefore, it is likely that this set of 12 genes represents key determinants of attachment in *P. putida*. A number of mutants isolated in this screen (LapA, LapF, LapH) had been identified before (Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008); other attachment determinants were unequivocally identified after analysis of mutants in reciprocal genes identified *in silico*

(i.e., GacS, RpoN, FlhB, FliF, FliC and LecA). In the set of genes identified with the random mutagenesis approach, it is worth noting that *pstS* was found as deficient in attachment and this is of interest because the PstS protein was recently implicated in *P. aeruginosa* attachment to and disruption of the integrity of cultured intestinal epithelial cell monolayers (Zaborina *et al.*, 2008). The mutant isolated in this study after random mutagenesis probed that the *in silico* identified “reciprocal gene” was indeed relevant for attachment.

Identification of common reciprocal genes in other strains and characteristics of mutants in other species of *Pseudomonas*. The bioinformatics and mutagenesis approach identified a set of 9 adhesion-related reciprocal genes common to *P. putida* and *P. aeruginosa* (Table 2). In contrast, the LapA, LapF and LapH proteins seem to be more specific to *P. putida* KT2440, and no clear ortholog was initially identified in *P. aeruginosa* for these genes (Table 2). To test the extent to which the reciprocal and non-reciprocal genes are distributed among *Pseudomonas* strains, we interrogated the genome sequence of other strains for the presence of these 12 genes. The results of this analysis are presented below (See Table 4).

Large adhesion proteins and related proteins. LapA and LapF are extremely long proteins (4000-9000 amino acids) and exhibit repetitive domains which make BLAST searches difficult, because the numerous repetitions influence the score’s P-values (Youssef-Coronado *et al.*, 2007). Within *P. putida* strains, the BLAST search indicated the presence of orthologs in most strains with >73% identity in certain segments of the aligned proteins (Table 4). In the strains in which the gene was present, the region maintains high synteny, and in strains in which the gene is lost, a cluster of genes

including LapF and the adjacent export system is absent. We found no ortholog of LapA or LapF in *P. syringae*, *P. mendocina*, *P. stutzeri* and a number of *P. aeruginosa* strains. For *P. fluorescens*, mutants in LapA are available which are deficient in adhesion to abiotic surfaces and are also impaired in attachment to plant seeds (Hinsa *et al.*, 2003). Recently a potential ortholog of LapA/LapF (BapA or PA1874) has been identified in *P. aeruginosa*, and a mutant is available in one of our laboratories (C. Giraud, and S. de Bentzmann unpublished). It has been shown that the BapA mutant is deficient in biofilm formation. Available experimental data support a general role of Lap proteins in adhesion in the genus *Pseudomonas*.

LapH corresponds to a protein annotated as an outer membrane protein that is highly conserved in *P. putida* strains F1, GB1, W619 and BIRD-1. This protein has significant homology to a number of other outer membrane proteins related to RND efflux pumps. In *P. putida* KT2440, LapH is part of a transporter system that places LapF on the cell surface to favor cell-to-cell interactions (Martinez-Gil *et al.*, 2010). We propose that in *P. putida* the highly conserved ORF PP0805 protein is required for export of LapF to the surface, and that the lack of LapF export is responsible for the impaired attachment phenotype in the ORF PP0805 mutant.

Lectins. LecA is a cytotoxic toxin produced by *P. aeruginosa* which binds with high affinity to hydrophobic galactosides (Diggle *et al.*, 2006). It has been shown that the *lecA* gene is expressed in biofilms, and a *lecA* mutant exhibited decreased coverage in biofilm formation (Chemani *et al.*, 2009). In *P. putida* it should be noted that the protein encoded by ORF PP1661 may be the result of a fusion between a LecA domain and an oxidoreductase, and that the original annotation of KT2440 overlooked the LecA domain (Nelson *et al.*, 2002). We obtained a mutant in this ORF with diminished

adhesion properties, and the mutant exhibited lower coverage of abiotic surfaces than the parental strain; these findings confirm the role of the *lecA* gene product in adhesion in *P. putida*.

In *P. putida* the ORF PP1661 forms an operon with upstream genes (ORF PP1659 and PP1660) that encode proteins of unknown function. This cluster of genes is present in *P. putida* strains F1, BIRD-1 and W619 with an identity >95% (Table 4). This cluster is absent in other *P. putida* strains, i.e. GB1, S16, and we suggest that its presence in KT2440 F1 BIRD-1 and W619 may be the result of its acquisition through potential horizontal transfer. Since in KT2440, F1, W619 and BIRD-1 the cluster is present within different genome sequences we suggest its acquisition by these strains may have represent different horizontal transfer events. Orthologs of the oxidoreductase domain of PP1661 are present in *P. fluorescens* and *P. aeruginosa*, but lower identities are found when the protein is sought in other strains of the genus *Pseudomonas* (Table 4). Orthologs of PP1661 are not present neither in *P. entomophyla* nor in *P. stutzeri* nor *P. syringae*. When we used only the LecA domain of PP1661 in the search, it was found only in *P. aeruginosa* strains (Table 4), suggesting a role for lectins in a limited number of *Pseudomonas* strains.

Flagella. Flagella have been described as attachment and rhizosphere colonization determinant in different *Pseudomonas* species (De Flaun *et al.*, 1990; O'Toole and Kolter, 1998 **a, b**?; Martínez-Granero *et al.*, 2006; Yousef-Coronado *et al.*, 2008). Feldman *et al.* (1998) reported that the flagellum of *P. aeruginosa* plays a role in virulence in a mouse model of acute pneumonia based on that a non-motile Δ *fliC* mutant caused local inflammation at the site of inoculation, but failed to disseminate throughout the mouse lung. The identification in this study of multiple flagellar proteins

required in the early steps of attachment in *P. putida* is of interest as a proof of concept of the approach used here, since the mutants were identified both in the analysis of reciprocal genes and after mutagenesis and selection of mutants deficient in attachment to polystyrene. Comparison of the genomic region of the flagella biosynthesis genes in *Pseudomonas* revealed, in general, a good degree of synteny, except in *P. stutzeri* and *P. mendocina*, and a relatively good degree of identity (Table 4), except for the FliC protein, the specific adhesion of the flagellum, what may influence the adherence properties of the different strain.

Regulators. In connection with the role of flagella in attachment, the role of sigma factor RpoN merits consideration since this factor is required for the expression of the FleQ/FleR proteins that control flagellum biosynthesis in *P. aeruginosa* and it was shown that the concerted action of (Dasgupta *et al.*, 2003) RpoN and the transcriptional activator FleQ was needed for the expression of *fliD*, the flagellar cap protein essential in adhesion to mucin (Arora *et al.*, 1998; Jyot *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, the RpoN phenotype related to deficient adhesion to abiotic and biotic surfaces is a clear case of pleiotropism. The *rpoN* mutants showed a significant reduction in adherence to epithelial cells and to tracheobronchial mucin (Ramphal *et al.*, 1991; Chi *et al.*, 1991; Simpson *et al.*, 1992). RpoN mutants have been used as controls defective in adherence in cell adhesion experiments and *in vivo* for studying the infection process (Comolli *et al.*, 1999). RpoN also negatively regulates the expression of SadB, an essential protein for surface adhesion (Caiazza & O'Toole, 2004). It was known that the RpoN protein is highly conserved in the genus *Pseudomonas* (Table 4).

GacS is the sensor kinase of a two-component system (GacS/GacA) that regulates a large number of genes, and it has been shown that the phosphorylated form of GacA

controls the expression of two small RNAs, *rsmY* and *rsmZ* (Brencic *et al.*, Mol Microbiol. 73:434). In *P. aeruginosa* and *P. fluorescens*, these two sRNAs serve as intermediates between input signals and mRNA stability. It has been shown before that the GacS kinase is required in *P. aeruginosa* for the expression of genes associated with chronic persistence, biofilm formation and the synthesis of autoinducers in the lung of patients with chronic cystic fibrosis (Parkins *et al.*, 2001; Mol Micro 40:1215, Reimann *et al.*, 1997 Mol. Microbiol. 24:309; Singh *et al.*, 2000, Nature 407,1677). Because GacS is present in all *Pseudomonas* with an identity >67%, this gene can be assumed to be a critical element related to surface recognition. Interestingly, mutants in the *gacA/gacS* system have been described in *P. fluorescens*, as showing a hypermotile phenotype (Navazo *et al.*, 2009) and thus might be locked in a planktonic state.

Others. PstS has been identified as a gene induced in *P. aeruginosa* under phosphate starvation conditions, and was annotated as a potential phosphate transporter (Madhusudham *et al.*, 2003). More recently it has been shown that PstS forms an appendage that is required for adherence to epithelial cells, and that *P. aeruginosa* PstS mutants were less virulent than their parental strains (Zaborina *et al.*, 2008). In *P. aeruginosa* the PstS protein was induced at phosphate concentrations below 1 mM (Lewenza *et al.*, 2005; Madhusudhan *et al.*, 2003; Nikate *et al.*, 1996; Poole and Hancock, 1986; Jensen *et al.*, 2006). We found that in *P. putida* PstS is also required for adhesion and that the PstS-deficient mutant was recovered in screening assays with phosphate-deficient medium such as LB. In microarray assays with KT2440 under P-starvation conditions, the *pstS* gene was induced more than 4-fold and we have observed that *P. putida* produces a kind of appendage under P-starvation conditions, which are similar to those reported by Zaborina *et al* (PLOS Pathogens 4:e43) in *P.*

aeruginosa. The *pstS* gene is present in all *P. putida* strains sequenced to date, as well as in *P. aeruginosa*, *P. fluorescens*, *P. entomophila*, *P. mendocina*, *P. syringae* and *P. stutzeri*. The degree of identity of PstS from all sources is higher than 80%. The appendage made by PstS may be a universal attachment factor in *Pseudomonas*, particularly relevant in P limited environments such as soils and gut tract of animals. It has been suggested that synthesis of PstS on appendages may confer an evolutionary advantage to *P. aeruginosa* by expressing phosphate acquiring structures capable of scavenging intracellular phosphate and facilitating attachment.

Our screening assays identified an ORF PP1663 as a potential adhesion protein. Orthologs with more than 60% identity to PP1663 are present in *P. aeruginosa* and other strains of the genus *Pseudomonas* (Table 4), but no mutants in this corresponding ortholog gene are available or have been studied with regard to attachment. The genome organization reflected a high degree of synteny in all *P. putida* genomes and lower synteny and degree of identity in strains of other species. Then, a role for PP1663 in attachment can only be suggested based on the results of the present study.

In summary, genome-scale comparisons to identify reciprocal genes constitute an approach that can be used to group genes according to metabolic function (Oberhardt *et al.*, 2011) or the physico-chemical characteristics of microbes; however, the *in silico* approach needs experimental support for unequivocal function assignment. Our bioinformatics and experimental data support that LapA and LapF are of relevance in *P. putida* and *P. fluorescens* with regard to attachment, LecA is of relevance in adhesion in *P. aeruginosa* and *P. putida* whereas GacS, RpoN and flagellum proteins are of universal relevance for adhesion in all pseudomonads. It follows that the different

lifestyles of different pseudomonads may be more related to the arsenal of metabolic and virulence genes that the set of genes these bacteria use to initially attach to biotic or abiotic surfaces.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Bacterial strains, plasmids, and culture conditions. The rifampicin-resistant *P. putida* KT2440R strain and its isogenic mutant strains were used in this study (Espinosa-Urgel *et al.*, 2000). *Escherichia coli* strains and plasmids used for transposon mutagenesis (CC118- λ pir harboring pUT-Km; HB101 harboring RK600) have been previously described (de Lorenzo *et al.*, 1990).

Escherichia coli strains were grown at 37°C in Luria-Bertani (LB) medium (Sambrook *et al.*, 1987). *Pseudomonas putida* strains were grown at 30°C in either LB or minimal basal M9 medium (Sambrook *et al.*, 1987) supplemented with Fe-citrate, MgSO₄, and trace metals (Abril *et al.*, 1989) and with citrate (15 mM) or glucose (0.4%, wt/vol) as a carbon source.

When appropriate, antibiotics were added at the following concentrations (in micrograms per milliliter): chloramphenicol, 30; kanamycin, 50; rifampin, 30; and ampicillin, 100. Rifampin was routinely used to select KT2440R or its derivatives, since this strain is resistant to this antibiotic.

Mutagenesis. Transposon mutagenesis with mini-Tn5-Km, a mini-Tn5 derivative carrying a kanamycin resistance marker (de Lorenzo *et al.*, 1990), was performed by triparental mating. The recipient (*P. putida* KT2440R), donor (*E. coli* CC118- λ pir

harboring pUT-Km, the suicide vector carrying mini-Tn5-Km), and helper (*E. coli* HB101 with pRK600) strains were grown overnight in LB with the appropriate antibiotics. We took 0.7 ml of recipient cells and mixed with 0.2 ml of the donor and 0.1 ml of the helper. Cells were collected by centrifugation, resuspended in 5 ml of 1×M9, and spotted on an LB plate. After 6 h of incubation at 30°C, cells were scraped off the plate and resuspended in 1 ml LB, and serial dilutions were plated on selective minimal medium (M9 with benzoate, kanamycin, and chloramphenicol).

Attachment to seeds and leaves. Corn seeds or *Vinca major* leaves were surface sterilized by washing twice for 15 min with 70% (vol/vol) ethanol and twice with 20% (vol/vol) bleach, followed by thorough rinsing with sterile deionized water (Molina-Henares *et al.*, 2010). Prior to the attachment experiments, seeds and leaves were routinely hydrated for 12 to 16 h. We have observed that this step increases bacterial adhesion to seeds (Espinosa-Urgel *et al.*, 2000).

The assays were performed as described by Espinosa-Urgel *et al.* (2000) and are summarized below. One microliter of overnight culture grown in LB was inoculated in 1 ml M9 basal medium, and one seed or one leaf was added to each bacterial suspension. After incubation for 1 h at room temperature, seeds or leaves were removed and washed thoroughly with deionized water. The tubes were vortexed for 1 min to remove any bacteria that may not have been tightly attached to the seed or leaf surface. Seeds or leaves were washed again and then disrupted by vortexing with 3-mm-diameter glass beads in M9 basal medium (Rodríguez-Herva *et al.*, 1999). This procedure does not affect bacterial viability. To estimate the percentage of cells attached to the seeds or leaves with respect to the number of inoculated cells, dilutions of the

resulting suspension were plated on selective medium. Each assay was repeated at least three times.

Biofilm formation assays. The formation of biofilms on abiotic surfaces was assessed essentially as described elsewhere (O'Toole and Kolter, 1998 a, b?). Cultures were grown overnight and inoculated (1:10 dilution) in 50 ml LB or M9, supplemented with casaminoacids (0.05% p/v) either benzoate or glucose, in polystyrene microtiter dishes. After 4 h of incubation at 30°C, the wells were washed with deionized water, and a 1% (wt/vol) solution of crystal violet was added to each well. Plates were incubated at room temperature for 15 min and washed thoroughly, and biofilm formation was quantified. For this purpose, the stain was solubilized by adding 70% (v/v) ethanol (200 µl twice) to each well. Absorbance at 540 nm was then measured in an ELISA reader.

DNA techniques. Preparation of plasmid and chromosomal DNA, digestion with restriction enzymes, electrophoresis, and Southern blotting were carried out using standard methods (Ausubel et al., 1987; Sambrook *et al.*, 1987). Hybridizations were done using the DIG DNA labeling and detection kit as instructed by the manufacturer. DNA sequences from the transposon mutants were determined using arbitrary PCR (Caetano-Annoles, 1993) with *Taq* DNA polymerase (Pharmacia) on an Applied Biosystem GeneAmp 9600 system. A first round of amplification was done by using the chromosomal DNA of the mutants as a template, with an arbitrary primer (ARB1; 5'-GGCACGCGTCGACTAGTACNNNNNNNNNGATAT-3') and an internal primer of mini-Tn5, unique for the right end (TNEXT; 5'-TGATGAATGTTCCGTTGCGCTGCC-3'). The first round was as follows: 3 min at 95°C; 6 cycles of 30 min at 95°C, 30 min at 30°C, and 1 min at 72°C; 30 cycles of 30

min at 95°C, 30 min at 50°C, 1 min 72°C, followed by and an extension period of 7 min at 72°C. A second round of amplification was done with 5 ml of the first-round reaction as the template, as follows: 3 min at 95°C; 30 cycles of 30 min at 95°C, 30 min at 57°C, 1 min at 72°C, followed by 7 min at 72°C. Primers used for the second round were those corresponding to the conserved region of ARB1 (ARB2; 5'-GGCACGCGTCGACT AGTAC-3') and a second internal primer of mini-Tn5 closer to the end (TNINT; 5'-GACCTGCAGGCATGCAAGCTCGGC-3').

Reaction mixtures were electrophoresed, and the most intense bands were isolated with a Qiagen gel extraction kit and sequenced. Sequencing was done on an ABI PRISM 310 automated sequencer, using oligonucleotide TNINT as a primer. The 40-bp distance between this primer and the end of the mini-Tn5 provides an internal control to ensure that the sequence obtained corresponds to the junction between the transposon and the chromosome. Sequences were analyzed and compared with the GenBank database by using BLAST programs (Altschul *et al.*, 1997).

Identification of pairs of reciprocal genes – genome-wide BLAST search. The identification of pairs of reciprocal genes from *P. aeruginosa* and *P. putida* was performed with WU BLAST software version 2.0 (© Gish, W., 1996-2003, <http://blast.wustl.edu>). Protein and nucleotide sequences for all *P. aeruginosa* and *P. putida* genes were downloaded from the *Pseudomonas* Genome Database V2 (<http://v2.pseudomonas.com>), and identification was performed as described in the Results section.

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Table 1. *In silico* pairing of *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 and *P. putida* KT2440 reciprocal genes encoding proteins potentially related to attachment.

<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1			<i>P. putida</i> KT2440			
Locus	Gene name	Product name	Locus	Gene name	Product name	% Identity
PA0338	--	hypothetical protein	PP_4405		diguanylate cyclase with PAS/PAC sensor	46.54
PA0395	<i>pilT</i>	twitching motility protein PilT	PP_5093	<i>pilT</i>	twitching motility protein	50.76
PA0408	<i>pilG</i>	twitching motility protein PilG	PP_4992	<i>pilG</i>	response regulator receiver protein	77.00
PA0409	<i>pilH</i>	twitching motility protein PilH	PP_4991	<i>pilH</i>	response regulator receiver protein	76.03
PA0410	<i>pilI</i>	twitching motility protein PilI	PP_4990	<i>pilI</i>	type IV pili signal transduction protein PilI	58.62
PA0411	<i>pilJ</i>	twitching motility protein PilJ	PP_4989	<i>pilJ</i>	type IV pili signal transduction protein PilJ	77.09
PA0413	<i>chpA</i>	component of chemotactic signal transduction system	PP_4988		chemotaxis protein CheA	68.02
PA0861	--	hypothetical protein	PP_1761		sensory box protein/GGDEF family protein	64.32
PA0928	<i>gacS</i>	sensor/response regulator hybrid	PP_1650	<i>gacS</i>	multi-sensor hybrid histidine kinase	66.44
PA1077	<i>flgB</i>	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgB	PP_4391	<i>flgB</i>	flagellar basal body rod protein FlgB	74.26
PA1078	<i>flgC</i>	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgC	PP_4390	<i>flgC</i>	flagellar basal body rod protein FlgC	83.67
PA1079	<i>flgD</i>	flagellar basal-body rod modification protein FlgD	PP_4389	<i>flgD</i>	flagellar basal body rod modification protein	57.79
PA1080	<i>flgE</i>	flagellar hook protein FlgE	PP_4388	<i>flgE</i>	flagellar hook protein FlgE	47.73
PA1081	<i>flgF</i>	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgF	PP_4386	<i>flgF</i>	flagellar basal body rod protein FlgF	71.08
PA1082	<i>flgG</i>	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgG	PP_4385	<i>flgG</i>	flagellar basal body rod protein FlgG	86.21
PA1083	<i>flgH</i>	flagellar L-ring protein precursor FlgH	PP_4384	<i>flgH</i>	flagellar basal body L-ring protein	80.95
PA1084	<i>flgI</i>	flagellar P-ring protein precursor FlgI	PP_4383	<i>flgI</i>	flagellar basal body P-ring protein	90.78
PA1085	<i>flgJ</i>	flagellar protein FlgJ	PP_4382	<i>flgJ</i>	flagellar rod assembly protein/muramidase FlgJ	55.24
PA1086	<i>flgK</i>	flagellar hook-associated protein 1 FlgK	PP_4381	<i>flgK</i>	flagellar hook-associated protein FlgK	41.73
PA1092	<i>fliC</i>	flagellin type B	PP_4378	<i>fliC</i>	flagellin FliC	64.16
PA1097	<i>fleQ</i>	transcriptional regulator FleQ	PP_4373	<i>fleQ</i>	sigma54 specific transcriptional regulator	84.06
PA1099	<i>fleR</i>	two-component response regulator	PP_4371	<i>fleR</i>	two component, sigma54 specific, transcriptional regulator	74.31

PA1100	<i>fliE</i>	flagellar hook-basal body complex protein FliE	PP_4370	<i>fliE</i>	flagellar hook-basal body protein FliE	74.55
PA1101	<i>fliF</i>	Flagella M-ring outer membrane protein precursor	PP_4369	<i>fliF</i>	flagellar MS-ring protein	72.95
PA1102	<i>fliG</i>	flagellar motor switch protein FliG	PP_4368	<i>fliG</i>	flagellar motor switch protein G	85.84
PA1103	--	probable flagellar assembly protein	PP_4367	<i>fliH</i>	flagellar assembly protein H	62.84
PA1104	<i>fliI</i>	flagellum-specific ATP synthase FliI	PP_4366	<i>fliI</i>	flagellum-specific ATP synthase	88.81
PA1105	<i>fliJ</i>	flagellar protein FliJ	PP_4365	<i>fliJ</i>	flagellar biosynthesis chaperone	64.63
PA1107	--	conserved hypothetical protein	PP_1411	--	GGDEF domain-containing protein	48.45
PA1443	<i>fliM</i>	flagellar motor switch protein FliM	PP_4358	<i>fliM</i>	flagellar motor switch protein FliM	88.79
PA1444	<i>fliN</i>	flagellar motor switch protein FliN	PP_4357	<i>fliN</i>	flagellar motor switch protein	80.62
PA1445	<i>fliO</i>	flagellar protein FliO	PP_4356	<i>fliO</i>	flagellar assembly protein FliO	59.30
PA1446	<i>fliP</i>	flagellar biosynthetic protein FliP	PP_4355	<i>fliP</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FliP	82.67
PA1447	<i>fliQ</i>	flagellar biosynthetic protein FliQ	PP_4354	<i>fliQ</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FliQ	77.53
PA1448	<i>fliR</i>	flagellar biosynthetic protein FliR	PP_4353	<i>fliR</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FliR	67.83
PA1449	<i>flhB</i>	flagellar biosynthetic protein FlhB	PP_4352	<i>flhB</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhB	67.81
PA1452	<i>flhA</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhA	PP_4344	<i>flhA</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhA	84.32
PA1453	<i>flhF</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhF	PP_4343	<i>flhF</i>	flagellar biosynthesis regulator FlhF	65.68
PA1454	<i>fleN</i>	flagellar synthesis regulator FleN	PP_4342	<i>fleN</i>	flagellar number regulator FleN	91.97
PA1460	<i>motC</i>	MotC	PP_4336	<i>motC</i>	flagellar motor protein	83.33
PA1461	<i>motD</i>	MotD	PP_4335	<i>motB</i>	flagellar motor protein MotD	70.08
PA1727	<i>mucR</i>	MucR	PP_3581	--	GGDEF domain-containing protein	65.94
PA2407	--	probable adhesion protein	PP_3801	--	periplasmic solute binding protein	84.64
PA2570	<i>lecA</i>	LecA	PP_1661	--	dehydrogenase	40.68
PA3115	<i>fimV</i>	Motility protein FimV	PP_1993	--	peptidoglycan-binding LysM	52.65
PA3385	<i>amrZ</i>	alginate and motility regulator Z	PP_4470	<i>algZ</i>	Arc domain protein DNA binding domain protein	85.85
PA3702	<i>wspR</i>	probable two-component response regulator	PP_1494	--	response regulator/GGDEF domain-containing protein	75.70
PA3703	<i>wspF</i>	probable methylesterase	PP_1493	--	chemotaxis-specific methylesterase	74.93

PA3704	<i>wspE</i>	probable chemotaxis sensor/effector fusion protein	PP_1492	--	chemotaxis protein CheA	69.31
PA3705	<i>wspD</i>	hypothetical protein	PP_1491	--	chemotaxis protein CheW	55.45
PA3706	<i>wspC</i>	probable protein methyltransferase	PP_1490	--	methyltransferase, CheR-like	51.52
PA3707	<i>wspB</i>	hypothetical protein	PP_1489	--	chemotaxis protein CheW	55.78
PA3708	<i>wspA</i>	probable chemotaxis transducer	PP_1488	--	methyl-accepting chemotaxis sensory transducer	69.56
PA3805	<i>pilF</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilF	PP_0851	<i>pilF</i>	type IV pilus biogenesis/stability protein PilW	55.95
PA4297	<i>tadG</i>	TadG	PP_0765		hypothetical protein	43.33
PA4367	<i>bifA</i>	BifA	PP_0914	--	GGDEF domain-containing protein	82.97
PA4462	<i>rpoN</i>	RNA polymerase sigma-54 factor	PP_0952	<i>rpoN</i>	RNA polymerase factor sigma-54	86.35
PA4525	<i>pilA</i>	type 4 fimbrial precursor PilA	PP_0634	<i>pilA</i>	fimbrial protein pilin	40.86
PA4526	<i>pilB</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilB	PP_1047	<i>xcpR</i>	type II secretion system protein E	42.79
PA4527	<i>pilC</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilC	PP_0633	<i>pilC</i>	type IV pili biogenesis protein PilC	45.01
PA4528	<i>pilD</i>	type 4 prepilin peptidase PilD	PP_0632	<i>pilD</i>	prepilin peptidase	64.36
PA4552	<i>pilW</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilW	PP_1052	<i>xcpW</i>	type II secretion pathway protein XcpW	51.61
PA4556	<i>pilE</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilE	PP_0611	<i>pilE</i>	type IV pili biogenesis protein PilE	49.06
PA4651	<i>cupE4</i>	pilin assembly chaperone CupE4	PP_2361	<i>csuC</i>	type 1 pili usher pathway chaperone CsuC	47.93
PA5040	<i>pilQ</i>	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis outer membrane protein	PP_5080	<i>pilQ</i>	type IV pilus secretin PilQ	58.72
PA5368	<i>pstS</i>	phosphate transporter, PstS	PP_5329	<i>pstS</i>	phosphate binding protein, adhesin	86.38
PA5498	--	probable adhesin	PP_0120	--	periplasmic solute binding protein	65.89

The column identify (%) refers to the degree of identity of the two paired proteins.

Table 2. Functional groups of *in silico* and experimentally verified attachment proteins in KT2440 and their reciprocal genes in *P. aeruginosa* PA01.

Group	Locus	Gene name	Product name	Biofilm	Reciprocal gen in <i>P. aeruginosa</i>
	KT2440			100	
Large adhesion proteins	PP_0168	<i>lapA</i>	surface adhesion protein	7.7	<i>bapA</i>
	PP_0806	<i>lapF</i>	surface adhesion protein	4.5	--
	PP_0805	<i>lapH</i>	TolC family type I secretion outer membrane protein	65	--
Regulators	PP_0952	<i>rpoN</i>	RNA polymerase factor sigma-54	47	<i>rpoN</i>
	PP_1650	<i>gacS</i>	multi-sensor hybrid histidine kinase	54	<i>gacS</i>
Flagella	PP_4352	<i>flhB</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhB	43	<i>flhB</i>
	PP_4369	<i>fliF</i>	flagellar MS-ring protein	54	<i>fliF</i>
	PP_4376	<i>fliD</i>	flagellar cap protein FliD	68	<i>fliD</i>
	PP_4378	<i>fliC</i>	flagellin FliC	74	<i>fliC</i>
Lectins	PP_1661	<i>lecA</i>	dehydrogenase subunit	2	<i>lecA</i>
Others	PP_1633	--	hypothetical protein	33	PAO 3611
	PP_5329	<i>pstS</i>	phosphate ABC transporter phosphate-binding protein	47	<i>pstS</i>

Table 3. Attachment of *P. putida* KT2440 and its isogenic mutants to maize seeds and *Vinca major* leaves.

Group	Locus	Gene name	Product name	Seed ¹ adhesion	Leaf ² adhesion
Wild-type	---	--		100	100
Large adhesion proteins	PP_0168	<i>lapA</i>	surface adhesion protein	5	50
	PP_0806	<i>lapF</i>	surface adhesion protein	25	20
	PP_0805	<i>lapH</i>	TolC family type I secretion outer membrane protein	32	24
Regulators	PP_0952	<i>rpoN</i>	RNA polymerase factor sigma-54	25	10
	PP_1650	<i>gacS</i>	multi-sensor hybrid histidine kinase	100	100
Flagella	PP_4352	<i>flhB</i>	flagellar biosynthesis protein FlhB	25	3
	PP_4369	<i>fliF</i>	flagellar MS-ring protein	25	5
	PP_4376	<i>fliD</i>	flagellar cap protein FliD	25	7
	PP_4378	<i>fliC</i>	flagellin FliC	25	15
Lectins	PP_1661	<i>lecA</i>	dehydrogenase subunit	32	100
Others	PP_1633	--	hypothetical protein	50	20
	PP_5329	<i>pstS</i>	phosphate ABC transporter phosphate-binding protein	100	20

¹ For seed adhesion corn seeds or were submerged in a solution containing about 10⁹ CFU/ml and upon exhaustive washing (see Experimental Procedures) attached cells were counted on selection plates. 100% adhesion corresponds to 2±1×10⁷ CFU/seed.

² For leave adhesion we submerged leaves in the bacterial solution as above. 100% adhesion corresponds to 4±1×10⁶ CFU/leave.

Table 4. Expression of adhesion genes in cells growing on LB or M9 medium.

Group	Locus	Gene name	LB	M9
	KT2440			
Large adhesion proteins	PP_0168	<i>lapA</i>	3650	3482
	PP_0806	<i>lapF</i>	571	570
	PP_0805	<i>lapH</i>	2419	1827
Regulators	PP_0952	<i>rpoN</i>	3839	451
	PP_1650	<i>gacS</i>	7481	13525
Flagella	PP_4352	<i>flhB</i>	1895	1346
	PP_4369	<i>fliF</i>	1968	1025
	PP_4376	<i>fliD</i>	14986	3264
	PP_4378	<i>fliC</i>	55691	10110
Lectins	PP_1661	--	1728	1781
Others	PP_1633	--	2103	1211
	PP_5329	<i>pstS</i>	772	9882
Control Internal calibrator		<i>gltA</i>	9883	17727
		<i>pobA</i>	640	920

Table 5. Identity of attachment determinants identified in *P. putida* with other strains of the genus *Pseudomonas*.

	PP_016 8 LapA	PP_080 5	PP_080 6 LapF	PP_095 2 rpoN	PP_165 0 GacS	PP_435 2 FlhB	PP_436 9 FliF	PP_437 6 FliD	PP_437 8 FliC	PP_166 1	Lec166 1	PP_163 3	PP_532 9 PstS
<i>P. putida</i> KT2440	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
<i>P. putida</i> F1	90	99	95	100	99	93	99	42	62	99	99	99	99
<i>P. putida</i> GB-1	79	96	88	99	97	96	99	48	65	--	--	93	98
<i>P. putida</i> W619	39	88	75	98	90	91	93	45	57	96	92	88	98
<i>P. putida</i> S16	73	24	--	98	94	96	98	62	60	--	--	94	98
<i>P. putida</i> BIRD-1	99	99	97	99	99	99	99	47	65	99	99	100	99
<i>P. fluorescens</i> PfO-1	42	25	--	92	75	72	86	44	61	32	--	58	89
<i>P. fluorescens</i> pf-5	42	28	--	91	75	74	87	42	67	24	--	59	89
<i>P. entomophila</i> L48	54	25	--	96	89	89	93	41	66	24	--	85	98
<i>P. syringae</i> DC3000	--	27	--	91	70	66	77	42	67	--	30	67	86
<i>P. syringae</i> B728a	--	30	--	90	71	67	78	45	67	--	--	65	85
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PAO1	--	26	33	86	67	68	75	36	48	26	41	66	86
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PA7	--	26	34	85	67	68	75	36	62	25	32	66	86
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PA14	--	26	34	86	67	68	75	36	48	26	41	66	86
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> LESB58	--	26	34	86	67	68	75	36	48	26	41	66	86
<i>P. mendocina</i> ymp	--	24	--	88	70	69	80	38	64	25	37	58	80
<i>P. stutzeri</i> A1501	--	--	--	82	68	67	78	47	75	--	--	61	81

Values are % of identify

LEGEND FOR FIGURES

FIGURE 1. Attachment of isogenic *P. putida* mutants to abiotic surfaces. Bacterial cells were grown on LB medium until they reached a turbidity of about 1 at 660 nm. The attachment assays to PS, PE and PP surfaces were done as described in Materials and Methods. The results are the average of three assays done in duplicate and the standard error is shown.

FIGURE 2. Biofilm formation by KT2440 and isogenic *P. putida* mutants.

FIGURE 3. Scanning electron microscopy of *P. putida* KT2440 and its isogenic mutants deficient in adhesion.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND METHODS AND SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pregrowth media and phenotypic assays in the phenotype microarrays. Individual colonies of *P. putida* KT2440 and mutant strains were picked from the surface of freshly grown cultures in LB medium plates supplemented with Rif, streaked onto M8 pregrowth (M8PG) medium plates (0.1 % [wt/vol] glucose, 0.1 g/liter NH₄Cl, 1mM MgSO₄ 0.6 mg/liter Fe-citrate, and micronutrients), and grown overnight at 30°C. Pregrowth of cells on M8PG medium was sufficient to deplete nutrient reserves such that the subsequent growth assays with different carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur sources were dependent on the nutritional sources provided. The biomass of the overnight plates described above was recovered from the plate surface and resuspended in 15 ml of M9 or M8 liquid medium to a turbidity at 660 nm (OD₆₆₀) of 0.2. The wells of the microplates were filled with 180 µl of the cellular suspension, and 20 µl of each carbon, nitrogen, or sulfur source was added to reach a final concentration of 5 mM. For sulfur source assays, the MgSO₄ in the M9 medium was replaced with MgCl₂. Positive control wells consisted of full minimal medium containing glucose, NH₄Cl, and MgSO₄ as carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur sources, respectively; negative-control wells contained medium without cell inoculate.

All data were recorded with a type FP-1100-C Bioscreen C MBR analyzer system (OY Growth Curves Ab Ltd., Raisio, Finland) at 30°C, with continuous agitation. The turbidity was measured using a wideband filter at 420 to 580 nm every 60 min over a

24-h period. Each strain was assayed at least three times for each of the compounds tested, and plates were visually examined after each assay to verify the results.

Carbon sources for phenotype arrays. The following carbon sources were used: aminobutyric acid, *L*-alanine, *L*-arginine, *L*-asparagine, *L*-aspartic acid, *L*-cysteine, *L*-glutamic acid, *L*-glutamine, *L*-glycine, *L*-histidine, *L*-isoleucine, *L*-leucine, *L*-lysine, *L*-methionine, *L*-phenylalanine, *L*-proline, *L*-serine, *L*-threonine, *L*-tryptophan, *L*-tyrosine, *L*-valine, 2-hydroxybutyric acid, 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid, 3-hydroxybenzoic acid, 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate, 4-hydroxybenzoate, acetic acid, *D,L*-mandelic acid, ferulic acid, formic acid, fumaric acid, glutaric acid, glycolic acid, homogentisate, ketobutyric acid, *L*-lactic acid, 7 malonic acid, potassium phthalate, propionic acid, quinic acid, sodium acetate, sodium benzoate, sodium lactate, sodium malonate dibasic, sodium pyruvate, succinic acid, trisodium citrate, tropic acid, *D*-arabinose, *D*-fructose, *D*-fucose, *D*-galactose, *D*-glucose, *D*-glucuronic acid, *D*-lactose, *D*-mannitol, *D*-ribose, *D*-sorbitol, maltose, *N*-acetyl-*D*-glucosamine, sucrose, trehalose, xylose, 2-phenylethylamine, 3-hydroxybenzotrile, 4-methylbenzoate, 4-nitrotoluene, 5 amino-*n*-valeric acid, adenosine, decanoic acid, glycerol, methylpyruvate, methylsalicylate, *m*-inositol, potassium thiocyanate, resorcinol, Tween 20, uridine, vaniline, propylbenzene, hexane, gallate, hexanoate, salicylate, 4-aminophenol, phenol, benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene.

Nitrogen sources for phenotype arrays. Nitrogen sources were the following 2-amino benzoic acids: *D,L*-homocysteine, *D,L*-ornithine, *D*-alanine, *D*-arginine, *D*-asparagine, *D*-aspartic acid, *D*-glutamic acid, *D*-histidine, *D*-leucine, *D*-lysine, *D*-methionine, *D*-phenylalanine, *D*-proline, *D*-serine, *D*-threonine, *D*-tryptophan, *D*- tyrosine, *D*-valine,

L-alanine, *L*-arginine, *L*-asparagine, *L*-aspartic acid, *L*-cysteine, *L*-glutamic acid, *L*-glutamine, *L*-glycine, *L*-histidine, *L*-homoserine, *L*-isoleucine, *L*-leucine, *L*-lysine, *L*-methionine, *L*-phenylalanine, *L*-proline, *L*-serine, *L*-threonine, *L*-tryptophan, *L*-tyrosine, *L*-valine, *L*- proline (trans-4-OH), Ala-Glu, Ala-Gly, Ala-His, Ala-Leu, Ala-Phe, Ala-Pro, Ala-Thr, Gly-Gln, Gly-Glu, Gly-Gly, Gly-Leu, Gly-Phe, Gly-Pro, Gly-Ser, Gly-Tyr, Gly-Val, Leu-Leu, Leu-Pro, Tyr-Ala, Ala-Ala-Ala, Gly-Gly-Ala, Gly-Gly-Gly, Gly-Gly-Leu, Ile-Pro-Ile, Leu-Gly-Gly, Lys-Lys-Lys, Val-Tyr-Val, 2,4-dinitrobenzoic acid, 3,4-dinitrobenzoic acid, 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid, 3-amino benzoic acid, 4-amino benzoic acid, 2-, 3- and 4-nitrotoluene, adenine, adenosine 5' diphosphate, agmatine sulphate, ammonium chloride, ammonium nitrate, *D*-(+)-glucosamine HCl, ethanolamine, ethylamine, formamide, hypoxanthine, inosine, *m*-toluidine, *N,N*-dimethylacetamide, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, *N*-acetyl-*D*-glucosamine, *o*-toluidine, phenylethylamine HCl, *p*-toluidine, putrescine, thiamine HCl, thymidine, triethylamine, uracyl, urea.

Sulfur sources for phenotype arrays. Sulfur sources were the following: *D,L*-ethionine, *D,L*-homocysteine, *D*-methionine, *L*-cysteine, *L*-methionine, sodium sulfate, taurine, 2-thiohydantoin, agmatine sulfate, cysteamine, *D,L*-alpha-lipoamide, *N*-acetyl-*L*-cysteamine, sodium sulfite, sodium taurocholate, thioflavin T, thiouracil, thiourea.

SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

Reference growth conditions for KT2440 in carbon, nitrogen and sulfur sources.

To rule out that defects in attachment were due to metabolic limitations we tested the wild-type strain KT2440 and the set of mutants for their ability to grow in the presence of 47 different carbon sources, 48 nitrogen sources and 16 sulfur sources using the

phenomics platform described before by Daniels *et al.* (2010). The reference conditions were set for the wild-type strain using ammonium chloride as the nitrogen source (carbon and sulfur assays), glucose as the carbon source (nitrogen and sulfur assays), and MgSO₄ as the sulfur source (carbon and nitrogen assays) (see *Supplementary Materials and Methods* above for complete descriptions).

The results confirmed that the ability of *P. putida* to use sugars as a C source was restricted to glucose, fructose, and glucuronic acid (a uronic acid structurally related to glucose). The results revealed the ability of *P. putida* to use organic acids (such as citric, glutaric, quinic, lactic and succinic acid), certain *L*-amino acids (Ala, Arg, Asn, Glu, His, Ile, Lys, Pro, Tyr, Val), and various aromatic compounds (3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetate, 4-hydroxybenzoate, homogentisate, sodium benzoate). We found that the wild-type KT2440 was able to use a number of amino acids (ornithine, Ala, Phe), dipeptides, ethanolamine, and adenine as an N-source but not as a C-source. Of note is the observation that KT2440 used a number of either *D*- or *L*-amino acids as an N-source when they were supplied as the sole nitrogen source (i.e. *D*-ornithine, *D*-alanine, *D*-arginine, *D*-asparagine, *D*-lysine and *D*-valine). Of the *L*-amino acids supplied as nitrogen sources, those that allowed KT2440 to grow (whereas *D*-forms did not) include *L*-Glu, *L*-His, *L*-Phe, *L*-Ser, and *L*-Tyr. Of the 17 sulfur sources tested, the wild-type strain was able to grow on 15. These include amino acids and organic acids, as well as other compounds such as cysteamine and thiouracil.

Phenomic analysis of the 12 mutants deficient in adhesion disclosed physiological differences only with the RpoN mutant. The most notorious difference between RpoN and the wild type was in the use of certain organic acids and dipeptides known to be

present in root exudates. In addition, growth of the RpoN mutant was delayed in the presence of heavy metals and some toxic drugs.

Motility analysis of knock-out mutants deficient in adhesion. Motility of all knock-out mutants was characterized on soft-agar plates. All adhesion mutants except those in flagellar genes were motile, and the motility of motile strains was similar to that of the parental strain.